

DETERMINATION OF THE QUANTITY OF WATER IN ETHANOL, GASOLINE AND ALCOHOL FUEL BY THE FISHER METHOD

Saloydinov Aziz Avazovich

Makhmudov Mukhtor Jamolovich

avazovichaziz 51@ gmail . com

PhD student basic doctoral studies at the Bukhara Institute of Engineering and
Technology Scientific adviser - Doctor of Chemistry, prof.
Uzbekistan, Bukhara

Usmonov Safar Bahronovich

Adizov Bobirzon Zamirovich

Director of the Bukhara College of Oil and Gas Industry
Scientific adviser - Doctor of Technical Sciences, old scientific collaborator
Uzbekistan, Bukhara

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7652673>

Abstract: This article describes the method of determining the amount of water in the gasoline-alcohol mixture and the fact that anti-knock additives form a dispersed phase in gasoline.

Key words: ethanol, solution, methanol, reagent, chemical process.

Water is a non-toxic and cheap powerful solvent. However, only a few organic reactions can take place in an aqueous environment. In addition, water has the ability to destroy many organic compounds and can cause side reactions in chemical processes. Therefore, it is desirable to determine the amount of water in each system. [1; 1-7 pp.]

Fischer's titration theory

To determine the amount of water in the composition of organic compounds, especially in ethanol, it is necessary to choose a reaction in which only water dissolved in this substance should react. This method can be used for many classes of connections.

This problem was solved in 1935 by the German scientist Karl Fischer. The fundamental principle of the Fischer method for determining the amount of water is based on the Bunsen reaction between iodine, sulfur dioxide and water. In doing so, Fischer found that excess sulfur dioxide, methanol as a solvent, and pyridine as a base (to buffer the solution) could be used to determine water in non-polar solvents.

Titration involves a three-step process:

In the first stage of these reactions, sulfur dioxide reacts with water and, as a result, is reduced to $I_2 I^-$ (reaction 1). The sulfur trioxide released as a result of this reaction forms a complex with pyridine (reaction 2), which, in the presence of methanol (or under the action of another alcohol), turns into a stable pyridine complex (reaction 3). Thus, for every equivalent of water, one equivalent of iodine is consumed.

The alcohol used is usually methanol and, in some cases, diethylene glycol.

The base used is pyridine, and in many cases imidazole or primary amines. Fisher's reactivation method.

In our studies, to determine the amount of water in the gasoline-alcohol fuel mixture by the Fisher method, we used the coulometric titrator "Ekros PE-9210". (Picture 1). Anhydrous methanol (400 ml, the amount of water in methanol should not exceed 0.3%) and dry pyridine (80 g) are placed in a 750 ml flask. Sulfur dioxide is passed through the solution under cold conditions until the mass of the solution increases to 20 g.

1 - picture. Overview of the coulometric titrator brand "Ekros PE-9210" for determining the amount of water in the ethanol-gasoline mixture by the Fischer method

Then 45 g of iodine are added, stirred until complete dissolution and incubated for 24 hours before use. The water equivalent of the reagent obtained by this method is 3.5 mg/ml. To check the compliance of the obtained reagent with the standard, it is tested in standard reagents with a pure amount of water in it, or a $Na_2C_4H_4O_6$ crystal is titrated.

Types of Fischer Titrations

Volumetric titration (for determination of water content from 100 ppm to 100%)

- For titration with a solvent, a titrant containing all the necessary components for Fischer's reagent is added to the sample from the burette (if the substance is liquid, then it can be used without a solvent);
- Iodine and an alcohol-containing shaker are added to a sample solution dissolved in a medium containing a base, sulfur dioxide and alcohol.

Coulometric titration (for determination of water content from 1 ppm up to 5%)

In this titration, iodine is generated electrochemically during the titration, and the amount of water is determined by the amount of total current passing through the coulometric cell. In this case, the titration result is determined using a microprocessor device and displayed on the screen.

In our studies, we used the method of coulometric titration.

References:

1. ГОСТР 54284— 2010 Нефти сырые Определение воды кулонометрическим титрованием по Карлу Фишеру Издание официальное Москва Стандзртинформ 2019
2. Makhmudov M.J. Adizov B.Z. Temirov A.H., A.A. Saloydinov Modification of Low-Octane Gasoline for Improvement of Its Environmental and Operating Characteristics International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology Vol. 7, Issue 6 , June 2020. P.1463-1471.
3. Махмудов. М. Ж. Тошев. М. С.,Салойдинов А.А. Гидроизомеризация бензолсодер-жащей фракции в присутствии катализатора ni/Al_2O_3 с целью доведения бензина до норм евро – 5 Science and education.,ISSN 2181-0842 volume 2, ISSUE 10 october 2021 104-111 б
4. Махмудов. М. Ж. Тошев. М. С.,Салойдинов А.А. Гидроизомеризация бензолсодер-жащих бензиновых фракций на катализаторе niw/Al_2O_3 с целью доведение автомобильного бензина АИ-80 до нормам евростандарту – 5 Science and education.,ISSN 2181-0842 volume 2, ISSUE 10 october 2021 135-140 б
5. Махмудов. М. Ж. Тошев. М. С.,Салойдинов А.А. Усовершенствование процесса региз для производства бензина соответствующего нормам евростандарту-5 Science and education.,ISSN 2181-0842 volume 2, ISSUE 10 october 2021 141-152 б
6. Салойдинов А.А., Эргашев. Ж. Ж. Альтернативные экологически чистые виды топлива для автомобилей Science and education.,ISSN 2181-0842 volume 3,ISSUE 4 april 2022 146-148 б

7. Махмудов М.Ж., Цуканов М.Н., Салойдинов А.А. Этанол асосли қўндирмаларнинг автомобил бензинлари детонацион барқарорлигига таъсирини тадқиқ қилиш Илмий-техникавий журнал.Фан ва технологиялар тараққиёти.No4/2021 Бухоро, 2021
8. Махмудов М.Ж., Салойдинов А.А. Турли функционал қўндирмаларнинг автомобил бензинининг экологик хоссаларига таъсири Илмий-техникавий журнал. Фан ва технологиялар тараққиёти. No4/2021 Бухоро, 2021
9. Махмудов М.Ж., Салойдинов А.А. Автотранспортларнинг экологик муаммолари ва автомобил бензинлари сифатига қўйилган замонавий экологик талаблар Илмий-техникавий журнал. Фан ва технологиялар тараққиёти. No2/2022 Бухоро, 2022

